

Supplemental Table S4 Top 20 enriched REACTOME_PATHWAY terms

Category	Term	Count	%	PValue	Genes	List Total	Pop Hits	Pop Total	Fold	Enrichment Bonferroni	Benjamini	FDR
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Platelet degranulation	8	5.970149254	2.57E-04	FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, CLU, KNG1, FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, CLU, KNG1, FGB, FGG, F13A1, F2, KNG1, FGB, VCAN, EFEMP1, LUM, COL14A1, FGG, BGN, EMILIN2, COL6A6, FBLN5, FGB, FGG, F13A1, F2, FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, F2, CLU, KNG1, VCAN, LUM, BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	129	10882	6.307034703	0.130461082	0.088205401	0.08788052
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Response to elevated platelet cytosolic Ca2+	8	5.970149254	3.25E-04	FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, CLU, KNG1, FGB, FGG, F13A1, F2, KNG1, FGB, VCAN, EFEMP1, LUM, COL14A1, FGG, BGN, EMILIN2, COL6A6, FBLN5, FGB, FGG, F13A1, F2, FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, F2, CLU, KNG1, VCAN, LUM, BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	134	10882	6.071697587	0.161750479	0.088205401	0.08788052
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Formation of Fibrin Clot (Clotting Cascade)	5	3.731343284	5.38E-04	F13A1, F2, KNG1, FGB, VCAN, EFEMP1, LUM, COL14A1, FGG, BGN, EMILIN2, COL6A6, FBLN5, FGB, FGG, F13A1, F2, FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, F2, CLU, KNG1, VCAN, LUM, BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	39	10882	13.03858136	0.253468289	0.093563111	0.093218495
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Extracellular matrix organization	11	8.208955224	6.89E-04	F13A1, F2, KNG1, FGB, VCAN, EFEMP1, LUM, COL14A1, FGG, BGN, EMILIN2, COL6A6, FBLN5, FGB, FGG, F13A1, F2, FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, F2, CLU, KNG1, VCAN, LUM, BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	301	10882	3.71664545	0.312285485	0.093563111	0.093218495
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Common Pathway of Fibrin Clot Formation	4	2.985074627	0.001209087	FGG, F13A1, F2, FGB, SERPIN A3, CLEC3B, FGG, F13A1, A1BG, F2, CLU, KNG1, VCAN, LUM, BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	22	10882	18.49107901	0.481560269	0.131306854	0.13082322
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Platelet activation, signaling and aggregation	9	6.71641791	0.004101009	F13A1, A1BG, F2, CLU, KNG1, VCAN, LUM, BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	263	10882	3.480260119	0.892624832	0.371141274	0.369774272
REACTOME_PATHWAY	ECM proteoglycans	5	3.731343284	0.006377745	BGN, COL6A6, ASPN C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	76	10882	6.690850959	0.969013584	0.494730821	0.492908608
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Regulation of Complement cascade	4	2.985074627	0.01067797	C4BPA, F2, CLU, STAT5B, MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	47	10882	8.655398688	0.997059912	0.724767187	0.722097695
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Signaling by cytosolic FGFR1 fusion mutants	3	2.23880597	0.012990723	MYO18A, LRRFIP1, COPS6, RAB5C, TFR, AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	18	10882	16.95015576	0.999175045	0.756797968	0.754010499
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Clathrin-mediated endocytosis	6	4.47761194	0.013937347	AAK1, PACSIN2, PACSIN3, C9, C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	146	10882	4.179490462	0.999510053	0.756797968	0.754010499
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Complement cascade	4	2.985074627	0.018818312	C4BPA, F2, CLU, FGB, SERPIN A3, NLRX1, RAB5C, PSMD14, SLC4A2, FGG, C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	58	10882	7.013857557	0.999966891	0.928940289	0.925518778
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Innate Immune System	18	13.43283582	0.027588858	C4BPA, A1BG, PA2G4, F2, CLU, ILF2, IFI16, C9, CAT, METTL7 A, LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	1063	10882	1.722123069	0.999999747	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Signaling by TCF7L2 mutants	2	1.492537313	0.028941475	LRRFIP1, CTBP2, CTBP1	107	38	10882	8.029021151	1	1	0.998154982

REACTOME_PATHWAY	Vesicle-mediated transport	13	9.701492537	0.03032839	RAB5C, TFRC, ANK2, HPR, NAPG, ARCN1, HPX, COPS6, SNX2, LMAN2, AAK1, PACSIN2	107	673	10882	1.964505423	0.999999945	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Regulation of Insulin-like Growth Factor (IGF) transport and uptake by Insulin-like Growth Factor Binding Proteins (IGFBPs)	5	3.731343284	0.033633156	, PACSIN3 VCAN, FGG, F2, CP, KNG1 STAT5B, MYO18A	107	125	10882	4.068037383	0.999999991	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	FGFR1 mutant receptor activation	3	2.23880597	0.036382799	, LRRFIP1 PFKFB2, RPL4, PSMD14, SLC44A2 , TACO1, LPL, AK4, SERPIN A6, LCLAT1, TYMP, GLS, MT- ATP6, MCEE, CA4, GC, CYP2J2, RPS9, LUM, GLRX5, SACM1L , BGN, TECRL, COQ7, RPL3L, DHODH, VCAN, PPA2, FXN FGB, LUM, FGG, COL6A6 STAT5B, MYO18A , LRRFIP1	107	31	10882	9.842025927	0.999999998	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Metabolism	29	21	0.048716047	, ATP6, MCEE, CA4, GC, CYP2J2, RPS9, LUM, GLRX5, SACM1L , BGN, TECRL, COQ7, RPL3L, DHODH, VCAN, PPA2, FXN FGB, LUM, FGG, COL6A6 STAT5B, MYO18A , LRRFIP1	107	2117	10882	1.393163487	1	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Integrin cell surface interactions	4	2.985074627	0.049978724	, LUM, FGG, COL6A6 STAT5B, MYO18A , LRRFIP1	107	85	10882	4.785926333	1	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Signaling by FGFR1 in disease	3	2.23880597	0.052654195	, LRRFIP1	107	38	10882	8.029021151	1	1	0.998154982
REACTOME_PATHWAY	Molecules associated with elastic fibres	3	2.23880597	0.052654195	EFEMP1, EMILIN2 , FBLN5	107	38	10882	8.029021151	1	1	0.998154982